

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SSEKAMULI****FIRST NAME: BENJAMIN****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR KABIRU GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanicsThe author did did not use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 16%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What practical writing tip helps to reduce anxiety and gives the researcher time to develop their ideas?
 - Start writing early.**¹
 - Setting a good hypothesis.
 - Sufficient review of the literature.
 - Starting with headings.
2. What is the most important reason for mentioning the information source one uses in their research?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 11.

- To uphold academic integrity and ethical standards by avoiding plagiarism, a serious academic offence that has serious consequences.²**
 - To show the extent of the literature review by the researcher.
 - To enhance the researchers' understanding of the study and that of the readers.
 - To ease the readability of the dissertation by any interested parties.
3. What forms the basis for a researcher to respond to the views of others and his reader's predictable questions?
- Interrogating secondary sources of information to find other's points of view and differing evidence.³**
 - The researchers' hypothesis and research questions.
 - The researchers' arguments and findings.
 - The researchers' methodology, results, and conclusions.
4. When is it appropriate to paraphrase information from the source?
- When the specific words of the passage are less important than its meaning, and the paraphrase is not being used as evidence.⁴**
 - When you cannot preserve the source and do not know whether you can access it later.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 34.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 50.

- When you need only the point in a passage, section, or even the whole book or article.
 - When you need to use the source as evidence.
5. What is appropriate paraphrasing?
- It is when the researcher represents an idea in their own words more clearly and pointedly than the source does.⁵**
 - It is when the researcher matches his words with those of the source.
 - It is when the researcher summarises the message in the source.
 - It is when the researcher re-writes the source's words but maintains the meaning.
6. What is the primary common purpose of citation across all the citation styles?
- To give the reader the information they need to identify and find the source.⁶**
 - To keep track of the sources used during the research undertaking.
 - To provide sufficient sources of evidence for the research.
 - To highlight the authors from which information is drawn for the research.
7. One of the citation styles commonly used in social, natural, and physical sciences is the author-date style. Why is it called author-date style?

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 81.

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 140.

- Because the author's name and publication date are critical elements for identifying sources.⁷**
- Because it is easy to identify the author using this style.
- Because it is well structured compared to other styles.
- Because it is superior to the other citation styles.
8. Why is it essential for researchers to collaborate?
- Because research potentially builds on prior research.⁸**
- Because of the cross-linkages in research methodologies.
- To support one another in conducting research efficiently and sharing knowledge.
- Because it avoids duplication of efforts by other researchers.
9. What must the research title be consistent with to avoid cognitive dissonance and confusion to the readers?
- The title must be consistent with the research questions.⁹**
- The title needs to be consistent with the hypothesis.
- The title must be consistent with the context within which the research is being conducted.
- The title must be consistent with the research variables.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 228.

⁸ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 10.

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 24.

10. What guides the researcher in the presentation of data analysis?

- The data analysis presentation must be guided by the research questions and hypothesis as appropriate.¹⁰**
- Data analysis techniques must guide the presentation of research questions.
- Research participants must guide the presentation of research questions.
- Research variables must guide the presentation of research questions.

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¹⁰ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 48.